

THE POSITION OF LANGUAGE COMPETENCE IN THE PREPARATION OF MEDICAL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The structure and content of educational and methodological support for the formation of the professional competence of a doctor in the direction of "psychological and pedagogical activity" is presented in the given article. The development of educational and methodological support was carried out on the basis of the labor functions of a doctor in accordance with the standards of professional activity.

Introduction

One of the important components of any professional activity is language and communicative competence. The modern Russian language is characterized by certain norms of its use, without knowledge of which a person cannot consider himself educated. Today, high language competence is an indispensable quality of a socially active person. The value and relevance of a specialist in the modern labor market largely depends on whether he has competent oral and written speech, the ability to communicate, to influence other people through the word. Violation of language norms, speech errors in the speech of even a very authoritative specialist in his field subjectively reduce the level of reliability of the information presented by him in the minds of those who listen or read. Psychologists warn that the deformation of speech can lead to a deformation of consciousness. In the training of a medical worker, the role of

studying the natural sciences and clinical disciplines is undeniable, but the ability of a worker to master his speech well, his ability to listen and hear, to correctly express his thoughts in writing is also very important. [4] The professional level of a medical specialist largely depends on the degree of his knowledge of language norms, oral and written speech. It's no secret that medical workers concentrate their attention only on the medical side of the patient's treatment and devote a minimum of time to communicating with him, that is, they treat the disease, not the person. This leads to difficulties in establishing contact between a medical professional and a patient, which can adversely affect the results of treatment, the mental state of the patient. [4]

Main part

The relevance of the topic is caused by the need to form a new generation of medical workers who can correctly express their thoughts. Purpose: improving the language

and communicative competence of a medical worker. The object of the study is the language competence of students of the Tuymazinsky Medical College. The subject of the study is the role of the language and communicative competence of future medical workers. Research objectives: The study of scientific literature on the topic under study. Assessment of the state of the language and communicative competence of students of the Tuymazinsky Medical College. Creation of an information bank of methodological material. Development of a long-term action plan to improve the language and communicative competence of students of the Tuymazinsky Medical College. The research hypothesis is the systematization of knowledge in the Russian language, which contributes to the formation of general and professional competence. Research methods were applied adequately to the set goals: study, analysis, processing of information from various sources; collection of statistical data; conducting a survey; interview. Stages of research: Studying the state of the issue from various sources of information at the moment (Internet, printed publications). Experimental work (questionnaire and survey materials) Analysis of the conducted research, development of plans, recommendations. Practical activities, summing up, evaluation of results. Conclusions and recommendations. The work has a theoretical and practical significance, as it opens up the potential in the spiritual and moral aspect of the formation of the professional and general competence of a medical worker, based on modern requirements, and makes it possible to use the results of the work in the practice of educational institutions, conducting

extracurricular activities. Even in antiquity, medical workers understood the importance of speech impact on the soul of the patient, and not just on the body. "Medic, cura aegrotum, sed non morbum!" "Doctor, treat the patient, not the disease. The saying attributed to Hippocrates speaks of a personal approach to each patient. The impact of the word is an important point in establishing contact between the doctor and the patient, which helps successful treatment. [2, p.5] Speech is the activity of a speaker who uses the means of language to communicate with other members of a particular language community or to address himself. Speech etiquette has the following functions: communicative, contact-establishing, calling functions, attracting attention, courtesy function, etc. The level of speech etiquette proficiency determines the degree of professional suitability of a person for linguistically active activities. [1, p.3]

Currently, many experts believe that it is necessary to gradually withdraw such concepts as "sick" from the process of communication and vocabulary, replacing them with the concept of a patient, due to the fact that the very concept of "sick" carries a certain psychological burden. And appeals to sick people like: "How are you, sick?" It is unacceptable to use, and it is necessary to try everywhere to replace such appeals to the patient with appeals by name, first name, patronymic, especially since the name itself for a person, his pronunciation, is psychologically comfortable. Communication with the patient is an essential element of the treatment process. [3, p.25] Medical terminology is rich, flexible and expressive. The aim of our project was to improve the

language competence of a medical worker. Main tasks: to draw attention to the problem of language and communicative competence of a medical worker. In order to identify the quality of knowledge of students of the medical college in spelling, orthoepy, psychology, an initial test was carried out. We offered 200 students (I-IV courses) to answer these questions. The results of testing and questioning surprised us. According to the test results, it was revealed that the first-year students showed good literate written and oral speech, but the questionnaire in psychology to identify communicative qualities turned out to be difficult for them. For students of the graduating groups, the questionnaire in psychology to identify communicative qualities did not cause difficulties, but the results of testing in spelling and orthoepy did not please us. Taking into account the data obtained, the circle developed a work plan among the students of the Tuymazinsky Medical College: Design a folder - a fold-out on the topic "Norms of communication of a medical worker." Supplement the ethical code of a student of the Tuymazinsky Medical College. Create a collection of multimedia presentations on the discipline "Russian Language and Literature" Create a memo "Speak correctly!" Create a trilingual dictionary "Medical terminology" Create a memo "Write correctly!" Conduct a class hour on the topic "The role of spiritual and moral and education in shaping the future professional medical worker"; Conduct class hours on the topic "Language competence of the future medical worker"; Shoot a video of the interview conducted in the city hospitals and Tuymazinsky Medical College. Write an article in the media about the need to improve the language and

communicative competence We decided to enrich the language and communicative competence of our students. After all, our great Russian writer I. S. Turgenev is right. "In days of doubt, in days of painful reflections about the fate of my homeland, you are my only support and support, O great, powerful, truthful and free Russian language!" After the work done, the members of the circle organized a second test, a survey among students of the Tuymazinsky Medical College. The survey showed that students realized the need to have a high level of linguistic and communicative competence. As a result of the survey, the following data were obtained: out of the total number of tested students, 91% answered correctly to all questions, 9% answered only a part of the questions. After conducting a secondary survey, we found out that professionalism and humanity are of great importance, but now the majority believe that knowledge of the Russian language at a high level, as well as ethics and deontology, influences the formation of their professional qualities as a medical worker. Taking into account the conducted research, we have come to understand the need for humane, cultural, competent education based on the experience of project work in this direction in college. The education of the spiritual, linguistic, moral, communicative qualities of a medical worker must begin with the study of the Russian language.

Conclusion

The study of this subject contributes to the development of professional qualities of the future medical worker. The analysis shows that in modern conditions sociability, literacy, patriotism are identified at the level of the following personal qualities - this is love for the big

and small Motherland, readiness to fulfill the constitutional duty, modern patriotic worldview, relevant attitudes and values, social tolerance, socially significant behaviors and activities. Currently, there are conditions when the demand for a medical worker in the labor market, his competitiveness largely depend on the availability of competent speech (oral and written), the ability to communicate effectively, on knowledge of the methods of speech influence, persuasion. It is today that interest in the Russian language is becoming a recognized necessity for millions of young people seeking to achieve success in life with the help of professional knowledge and skills. The richness, diversity, originality and originality of the Russian language allow everyone to make their speech rich and original. It should be remembered: a gray, illiterate speech filled with verbal clichés does not evoke the necessary associations in the minds of the listeners. It is unlikely that a person who abuses standard expressions can excite listeners, convince them of something, influence them. Based on the results of the work, the following conclusions were drawn: - A competent presentation of one's thoughts is one of the integral directions in the formation of the professional qualities of a future medical specialist. - A high level of linguistic and communicative

competence contributes to the education of professionals who meet modern requirements within the framework of the Priority National Health Project, and the ethical ideas of the population about medical workers. - The correct pronunciation of professional terms contributes to the development of language competence, as well as the enrichment of the general outlook (history, antiquity, etymology of words, etc.) Recommendations for students and the teaching staff of the college: - to systematize the study of the language and communicative competence of a medical worker; - pay great attention to the development of the language competence of future medical workers in the study of each clinical discipline; - replenish the dictionary of medical terms in different languages. So, we see that in medicine there are a lot of diverse and original concepts. It is important not only to know the terms and concepts, but also to understand their meaning, to apply them correctly in your speech and writing practice. In addition, poor, linguistically poor speech is perceived as a negative characteristic of a person, indicating his superficial knowledge, low linguistic and communicative competence, and insufficient vocabulary.

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